

Rethinking and “redwelling” a course in Architectural History

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Abstract — In the degree of Architecture of the School of Architecture La Salle, the subject “History of architecture 3” has collaborated in the activities of the pedagogical platform “Thinking Dwelling”, designed to promote the interrelation between diverse subjects of architecture programmes of the participating institutions in the European project OIKONET. The tasks designed to intertwine the subject with the collaborative learning platform are described, and the results of learning assessed.

Keywords - dwelling; housing; architectural history; learning spaces; blended-learning.

I. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, most higher education institutions are addressing the study of housing from a disciplinary perspective, for example by considering it from the architectural, urban or economic point of view. Likewise, in the academic programmes of architectural schools the study of housing is also addressed – in the best of cases– within a particular subject-matter (e.g. design studio, urban planning, architectural history...) rather than as a transversal matter.

One of the aims of OIKONET –a project carried out with the support of the European Union from 2013 to 2016– has been to create collaborative learning spaces that bring together a diversity of subject-matters from 19 schools of architecture and planning from 17 countries worldwide which were partners in the project. These collaborative learning spaces adopt a blended-learning approach, combining off-site and on-line activities. Before the advent of ICT in education, the term “learning space” has been used to refer to the physical environment where education takes place [1]. However, Punie [2] used this term to describe ICT-enabled educational spaces which transcend existing limits, physical, conceptual and institutional; educational environments in which students would be at the centre of learning, becoming co-producers of contents.

In the OIKONET project, we used the term “learning space” [3] to refer to pedagogic environments as those described by Punie [2]. More precisely, a learning space refers to

- A space that brings into relationship schools from different countries, which include housing, studies in their curriculum.

- A space that puts into relationship subject-matters (regular courses, seminars, design studios) from different academic

programmes addressing housing from multiple perspectives (architectural design, urban planning, representation, architectural theory).

- A space to support the exchange of knowledge among learners from different cultural background and academic levels.

- A space to design and implement learning activities in collaboration, with the participation of teachers and students from various schools.

- A space for collaboration that coexists with the regular academic activities that take place in each institution.

A. *Thinking Dwelling*

“Thinking Dwelling” is a learning space whose purpose is to bring together students and faculty from the OIKONET partner schools in a joint reflection on the forms of living in the contemporary world. Participants –students and teachers– are encouraged to reflect on the forms of dwelling in our global societies and to critically think about the role of the architect in the shaping of the spaces we inhabit.

The reflections on contemporary forms of dwelling are framed around three topics:

- **Representing**

To provide examples of ways of living through different art forms. For example, the relationship between inhabitants and space expressed in a film scene, a painting, a photograph, a passage from a book, a piece of music...

- **Experiencing**

To express the relationships with the spaces we live in, using any form of representation: a drawing, a video, a photograph, a text, a sound, in any combination.

- **Projecting**

To collect personal experiences about renowned houses, to comment on relevant examples of housing design.

The activities carried out in the joint learning space are intertwined with the courses that take place at each partner organization. The teacher in charge of a regular course in a particular institution creates ad hoc liaisons between this and the joint programme. In the first two editions of the learning space “Thinking Dwelling” which took place in 2015/16 and 2016/17,

several types of courses (architectural and planning design studios, history and theory courses) from schools in various countries (Spain, Puerto Rico, France, Belgium, Turkey) proposed a variety of activities to interface with the joint collaborative space [4].

A web-based environment has been specifically created to support the pedagogic activities in this learning space (www.oikonet.org/thinking_dwelling). In the public home page, the objectives of the programme are explained and a selection of submitted works is displayed. Users need to log in to upload works and see the works by other users.

The students' submission adheres to a standardized format: a title, a short description and an attached file (e.g. image, video, text). Then, they can group the works submitted by the participants in groups, and add comments on other people's work (Figure 1). This way, the collective work becomes a shared learning resource (Figure 2), which can be used to carry out further activities (e.g. to discuss in class the contributions made by students from other schools, to comment on their works, to design a new learning activity based on the experience of a previous one, etc.).

Figure 1. A work submitted to the platform “Thinking Dwelling”

Figure 2. Repository of works uploaded by participants

II. INTERLINKING “ARCHITECTURAL HISTORY” WITH “THINKING DWELLING”

A. Introduction

During the academic years 2016-2017 and 2017-2018 the subject “History of architecture 3” of the third year has participated in the pedagogical programme “Thinking Dwelling”. This participation has led to a renewal of

methodology and content of the subject, as well as the revision of some of the evaluation activities. The course addresses the architecture of the second half of the twentieth century, a period characterized by criticism of the tenets of the Modern Movement.

Regarding the content of classes, the axis of the discourse has been changed to focus on the conception of “living” proposed by architects critical of modern architecture. Starting from the poetic and dilated (almost omni-comprehensive) notion of “dwelling” by Heidegger [5], we have approached the debate of contemporary living, without losing sight of fundamental bases that, in relation to the housing programme, were laid by the Modern Movement.

Secondly, we have changed some of the assessment activities carried out outside the classroom to determine the final grade of the subject. The “Thinking Dwelling” learning platform puts at our disposal the possibility of making public the reflections by the students –and by the teachers–, and sharing them with the learners from other universities. Naturally, we could not miss the opportunity to participate in this learning scenario, although, to make our contributions visible, we should adapt to the format of the activities proposed on the platform, and find a way to link them with the content and objectives of our subject.

The need to adapt to platform’s format of activities delivery (concise texts, along with graphic media) led us to the following reflections: To get students to understand and assimilate the contents of the “History of architecture 3” agenda, does it make sense to ask them to take photographs? And, is it positive for students to write their reflections in short texts? After two courses participating in “Thinking Dwelling”, the results suggest that the answer to both questions is affirmative.

In past courses, the students of the subject “History of architecture 3” presented weekly drawings of some of the buildings studied in class, as part of their evaluation activities. Presumably, these drawings helped familiarize them with some of the masterpieces examined in class. The result was satisfactory, in the sense that the vast majority of students fulfilled the task correctly, although it was difficult to determine their degree of intellectual involvement in that work, since there was a possibility that it would become a mechanical, poorly thought out reproduction of an image.

But, what if it were proposed to photograph concepts, instead of buildings? That was the objective of photographs: to provide a close example of “living”, identifying the discourse of an author in the environment closest to the student. On the other hand, one of the transversal competences of the History of Architecture subjects is to enhance written expression, something that, gradually, has become a serious challenge for university education. In this sense, through the tasks performed in “Thinking Dwelling”, we have adopted a short writing format to convey what it means to “inhabit”. That brevity has intensified the demand for the content to be impeccable.

B. Dynamics of the “weekly task for Thinking Dwelling” of the 2016-2017 academic year

Each of the classes of the subject was devoted to presenting the work of an author of the second half of the 20th Century, such

as Alvar Aalto, Louis I. Kahn or Alison+Peter Smithson. During the lesson a slide was projected where a short quotation was presented, written by the same author object of study, in which some of the basic ideas exposed in the class on their notion of “dwelling” is synthesized. In the face of the quotation, students were invited to comment aloud on its content and a small debate about that quotation was opened to facilitate the understanding of its meaning. From that moment, students had a week, until the beginning of the next lesson, to provide an example of their immediate environment in which the main message of the quotation could be identified. That example was the “weekly task for Thinking Dwelling” which accounted for 20% of the final grade of the subject. The task consisted in presenting a photograph accompanied by a short writing, of only 130 words, being strictly obligatory that both the image and the text were original. It was recommended that students submit their proposals via email two days before the deadline to receive a written comment from their teacher to help guide or improve their work.

The grade of each of these weekly tasks was communicated within a week by email, including a summary of the reasons for this rating, with the intention to help students to improve their performance in the following tasks and to avoid the repetition of errors. Among all the tasks delivered each week, the most outstanding ones were selected and their authors introduced them on the “Thinking Dwelling” platform.

C. *Dynamics of the “monthly comment for Thinking Dwelling” of the 2017-2018 academic year*

Working on the same agenda as in the previous course, the new students of the subject in the 2017-2018 academic year had to submit a monthly task in which the subject studied in class was related to the weekly tasks introduced in the “Thinking Dwelling” portal by the students of the 2016-2017 course.

The format of this collaboration consisted of writing a comment of around 130 words. Since the task was delivered monthly, students had to choose one of the last four lessons to develop their commentary, while they also had to select one of the weekly tasks for “Thinking Dwelling” of the 2016-2017 course. Thus, combining the information of the last classes and browsing the works available in the “Thinking Dwelling” portal, each student was able to find out relationships between both sources, which were specified in their comment.

The comment had to satisfy two mandatory requirements that affected the grade if the students did not observe them. On the one hand, it was essential for the text to include the name of the architect studied in class whose ideas stimulated the student's comment; that is to say, it was not possible to generalize or allude in an abstract or nebulous form to any aspect mentioned in class, but it was required to specify the architect who represented a concrete position. Secondly, students were asked to make an effort to indicate specific elements of the photographs they commented on: “the closed window”, “the lamp hanging from the ceiling”, “the sitting character on the right”, etc. The two requirements were that the commentary should draw solid and clearly identifiable links between the syllabus of the subject and the weekly tasks of the previous course. Similarly to the previous operation, students were advised to make a pre-submission two days before the time limit

to correct their text. Then, they received the reasoned grade a week after via email. The comments that obtained better qualification were introduced on the platform “Thinking Dwelling” by their authors.

III. PEDAGOGICAL EVALUATION OF THE EXPERIENCE

The involvement of students with the tasks for “Thinking Dwelling” throughout the two academic years has been outstanding. More than 90% of the students have regularly handed in the activities, surpassing the commitment observed in the previous courses, when that percentage of the grade was destined to the realization of drawings. In addition, about one third of students submitted their proposals in advance to correct them, before final delivery. In all cases, there was an increase in the quality of the exercises after carrying out two or three tasks.

But the most outstanding fact has been perceived in class: students who have done the tasks for “Thinking Dwelling” remember better the subject matter of previous lessons, so they are much more prepared to relate the content of classes. The reason for the improvement in the assimilation of the subjects may be due to greater personal involvement of students throughout the new tasks. A decisive element is to reward the highlighted exercises with their introduction on the “Thinking Dwelling” platform, since it arouses the enthusiasm of the participants and, consequently, more effort is devoted to achieving a good result.

Similarly, for the students of the 2016-2017 course, it is a great satisfaction to note that their classmates in the following year have taken their activities to comment on. But, even more relevant than all that, is that students tend to devote the task to rediscovering their domestic environment, thus sharing a portion of their most intimate domains, through an exercise that makes them narrators of their own daily life, allowing them even to unveil the ideas of great architects between the rooms of their house. In other words, the intimacy becomes “extimacy” [9] thanks to this task: the student risks showing their home and dares to be evaluated for it. A task that involves that emotional component could be an appropriate method to explore the emotional dimension of “dwelling”.

This way, the past would appeal to the present and, thus, the architectural history –which is concerned with the causes and consequences of an architectural production immersed in the complexity of each historical period– would become, for an instant, an element of reflection of the student's present.

IV. LIAISON ACTIVITIES: EXAMPLES OF STUDENTS’ WORK

These are examples of students’ works carried out in three activities specifically designed to create a link between the course and the joint learning space “Thinking Dwelling” during the academic years 2016-2017 and 2017-2018:

A. Tasks about Alvar Aalto's quote

«The tubular steel chair is surely rational from technical and constructive points of view. It is light, suitable for mass production, and so on. But steel and chromium surfaces are not satisfactory from the human point of view»

Alvar Aalto. *The Humanizing of Architecture* (1940) [6].

Figure 3. Photograph by Adrián Haro (October 2016)

«This building is a simple, uninteresting block of houses located in Sao Paulo. We could find hundreds of buildings like this one, as if they had been produced in series. Its façade displays two colours, white and grey. The building lacks vitality, as though it was the extension of the adjoining dull road, with its lanes turned into building's windows. We can consider this block of flats technically rational and useful, as it fulfils the main function for which it was conceived, which is to allow for housing. However, from the human point of view, it looks gloomy and boring. This is why someone has transformed one of the external party walls of the building to give it a fresh life, in other words, a human touch», Description by Adrián Haro (October 2016)

«One big contrast, alive vs. dead colours. At the left, the façade of a block of flats with jail appearance; at the right a graffiti giving life to the building, giving it a personality. The block is standard, functional and rational; however, it looks very boring and sad. Inspired in Alvar Aalto's projects, the colourful graffiti humanizes the building, thinking about the emotions of the people living in it. The graffiti also manifests the human imperfections, as we can see in the disproportioned hands of the woman and in her face, as well as the organic shapes. The artwork also gives a sense of freedom compared with the jail looking façade, and the woman looking to the opposite side is giving the statement of "This is not us! It is not our nature!"», Comment by Favel Bermúdez (October 2017)

B. Tasks about Louis I. Kahn's quote

«The stair is the same for the child, the adult and the old. It is thought of a precise in its measures, particularly for the young boy who aspires to do the floors in no time flat, both up and down. It is good also to consider the stair landing as a place to sit near a window with possibly a shelf for a few books. The old man ascending with the young boy can stop here, showing his interest in certain book, and avoid the explanations of infirmity. The landing wants to be a room»

Louis I. Kahn. *The room, the street and human agreement* (1971) [7].

Figure 4. Photograph by Daniel Garcia Collell (October 2016)

«The stair landing enables a more noble turn while moving up and down. Moreover, it allows us to rest between two flights of stairs. Furthermore, as the picture shows, the stair landing can be imagined as something else, for it may provide us with a tiny, cosy seat, where one can rest without obtruding upon the everyday use of the stairs», Description by Daniel Garcia Collell (October 2016)

«This image shows us the humanistic way in several particular elements, taking care of every detail as Alvar Aalto did. You can see that the main objective of this place is to display a welcoming atmosphere thanks to the use of wood, marble and ceramic materials in warm colours, which protect the visitor with an attitude that embraces them. So much so that it has a rounded chair to resting near the window, a natural source of light that allows reading if necessary. A woody handrail gives a touch in the cosiest way, at the same height as the socket, so much that they seem the same element. The stair corners have a wooden finish with a rounded contour in order to protect the user, looking for comfort in their path», Comment by Mariona Carceller Balasch (November 2017)

C. Tasks about Smithsons' quote

«We were concerned with the seeing of materials for what they were: the woodness of wood; the sandiness of sand. With this came a distaste of the simulated, such as the new plastic of the period —printed, coloured to imitate a previous product in “natural” materials»

A+P Smithson. *The “As Found” and the “Found”* (1990) [8].

Figure 5. Photograph by José Lozano Nava (October 2016)

«This is an old building in Raval (Barcelona), which clearly shows what A+P Smithson were saying. Here we can see the woodness of the wood, the brickness of the brick etc. We can observe how this interest in leaving the materials exposed is present in our time, as the tiles and iron were left visible without imitating any other material. This example may follow the brutalist movement or be a new trend, but it shows an explicit criticism against “the simulated”, as the Smithsons would say», Description by José Lozano Nava (October 2016)

«Facing this side of the room I see this honest brickwork, along with exposed wooden structure beams below the Catalan vaults. Also, to my left a steel handrail, simple and raw with a truth colour to the material. I see the genuine face of architecture, which somehow reminds me of the new brutalism, A+P Smithson's ideas of using materials “as found”. I see the materials very much in the same way as they left the factory, shown with big confidence. As if this room was a theatre and these materials were given the main acting roles after given their trustworthiness to the act», Comment by Halwest Mustafa (December 2017)

V. CONCLUSIONS

The joint tasks that interlink the subject of “History of architecture 3” and “Thinking Dwelling” have allowed to bring, more than before, the subject to their students, inviting them to reflect on the multiple meanings of “dwelling”, including their own experience of the term. At the same time, the activities have become popular among the students, who visit the platform, with curiosity, to learn about the latest contributions from their classmates. For all these reasons, it seems justified that the tasks remain valid in the next courses. However, there will be aspects to be improved or reconsidered. Firstly, students should be given more critical elements about the photographic practice, in order to improve the quality of the images they produce, something that escapes the material possibilities of the subject of architectural history. Secondly, the two different tasks developed in the courses 2016-2017 and 2017-2018 could be alternated in a single course, proposing to the students that they combine the delivery of photographs with the contribution of comments to the activities of other users. To recap, we have begun to build our dwelling on the “Thinking Dwelling” platform. We hope to learn, now, to live in it.

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